

Degrees of Freedom - 8T

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the new 8T, and in particular the EL operator in which was used to derive the main equation, it is possible to analyze the structure of the multiverse from a different angle. That is by setting the operator to an infinite system of partial differential equations and infinite degrees of freedom – which comes to an agreement with our second representation, universe packets.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Up until now, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. In the 8T thesis we have derived the main equation () by EL operator. The following way:

$$\ell = (s, s', t)$$

We can state that the 8T analysis in that form has one degree of freedom.

$$\ell = (s_1, s'_1, t)$$

since we have proven the second representation in equation (1.2), and thus we can represent the EL operator as a system of differential equations with an infinite degrees of freedom. Those differential equations describe a system of stationary manifolds. That is a different way to state that we are dealing with an infinite dimensional universe, using the original operator.

$$\ell = (s_1 \dots s_n, s'_1 \dots s'_n, t_{1 \rightarrow n}) \quad (1.6)$$

the time operator is of course present in each manifold, but since each manifold has a unique moment of singularity, each manifold is getting flattened in different temporal moment, we have to index the time parameter, so to indicate that the arrow is in different stages for each manifold. Such a representation allows us to eliminate the question regarding the arbitrary number of 13.7B billion years. Equation (1.6) is another way to represent the structure of the multiverse, infinite manifolds that are stationary, and interact with each other. Since each manifold is part of the packet, it is confined by it and cannot escape the variation of the manifold than can be presented only within the domain of the packet. Such an analysis also eliminate the question of three dimensional universe, by representing infinite degrees of freedom, we can elevate the universe to infinite dimensions. We can represent the packet in a discrete way, for example:

$$\begin{aligned} s_1 &\rightarrow \text{dimen..}(1 \rightarrow 3) + t_1 \\ s_2 &\rightarrow \text{dimen..}(4 \rightarrow 6) + t_2 \\ s_3 &\rightarrow \text{dimen..}(K \rightarrow K + 2) + t_K \\ K &\in \mathbb{R} \end{aligned}$$

Since we already presented a symmetry regarding the universe packet, we can change the index of the summation with no effect. Residents of the "second manifold" regard themselves as first, and thus count their dimensions as first to third, if we are residents of the "first" manifold, we count our three as the first to the third, and "theirs" as fourth to six. Each resident of distinct manifold regard "his" dimensions as the lowest, i.e. first to third plus a unique arrow.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)